

Switching from hexane to sustainable solvents for defatting oilseed and fish biomasses in food processing

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Background/Problem

Conventional defatting/oil removal for both oilseeds and fish biomasses commonly relies on petrochemical solvents like hexane, which raise concerns about solvent residues, environmental pollution, and operator safety risks.

Practice Change

Full or phased replacement of hexane-based defatting with safer, more sustainable extraction options, selected to fit the facility's product, equipment, and throughput, while maintaining oil yield and product quality.

Evidence

Hexane extraction is compared with alternative "clean" solvents used across seed and fish oil processing. This includes via alcohols, terpenes, deep/natural deep eutectic solvents, ionic liquids, 2-methyloxolane, supercritical CO₂, and vegetable oils.

Setting/Participants

Food manufacturing facilities performing defatting of oilseed meals and/or fish biomasses; process engineering, quality, and production teams.

Implementation Plan

Screen solvent candidates for product compatibility, safety, and regulatory fit, prioritizing practical "drop-in" options, run pilot trials to compare yield, quality, and solvent recovery against hexane. Refine any needed pretreatments to boost extraction efficiency and evaluate scale-up needs before phasing implementation line by line.

Outcomes/Measures

Oil yield and residual oil in meal; solvent residues; product sensory/functional quality; worker exposure and incident rates; solvent recovery efficiency; energy use; unit cost per kg processed; environmental metrics.

Conclusion

Implementing sustainable defatting solvents can reduce safety and environmental risks associated with hexane while supporting effective oil removal, provided that solvent selection, pre-treatment optimization, and scale-up economics are addressed early in the rollout.

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Solvents such as 2-methyloxolane can be derived from renewable biomass

Supercritical CO₂ extraction leaves no organic solvent residue

Lower volatility and flammability risks